

Quantitative Nasal Eosinophilia: An Objective Tool to Optimize Intranasal Topical Steroid Spray in the Management of Perennial Pediatric Allergic Rhinitis

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Abstract:

Background: Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a common and chronic condition in pediatric populations, significantly impacting quality of life, school performance, and sleep. Intranasal corticosteroids are a primary treatment, but optimizing their use remains a challenge. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of quantitative nasal eosinophilia as an objective tool for optimizing intranasal topical steroid spray in the management of perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis.

Methods: Fifty pediatric patients diagnosed with perennial allergic rhinitis were enrolled. Inclusion criteria included ages 6-18 years and a clinical diagnosis of AR. Exclusion criteria involved concurrent respiratory infections or chronic illnesses. Nasal eosinophil counts were measured before and after treatment. Symptom severity scores were also recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean nasal eosinophil count significantly decreased from 15.2 cells/HPF at baseline to 5.8 cells/HPF post-treatment ($p < 0.001$). Symptom severity scores also improved significantly, from a mean of 7.4 to 3.1 ($p < 0.001$). No significant adverse effects were reported, indicating good tolerance of the treatment.

Conclusion: Quantitative nasal eosinophilia is an effective tool for optimizing intranasal steroid spray use in managing perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis. The treatment significantly reduces nasal eosinophil counts and symptom severity, improving clinical outcomes.

Recommendations: Further research should explore long-term effects and potential benefits of integrating nasal eosinophilia measurements into routine clinical practice for pediatric AR management. Additionally, larger sample sizes and multi-centre studies could validate these findings.

Keywords: Allergic rhinitis, Pediatric, Nasal eosinophilia, Intranasal corticosteroids, Perennial rhinitis

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Introduction

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a prevalent chronic condition characterized by inflammation of the nasal mucosa, which manifests through symptoms such as sneezing, rhinorrhea, nasal obstruction, and nasal itching. In pediatric populations, AR significantly impacts quality of life, school performance, and sleep quality, and is often associated with other atopic conditions like asthma and conjunctivitis [1].

The incidence and prevalence of pediatric AR have been rising steadily over the past decade. A systematic review and meta-analysis found that the overall prevalence of physician-diagnosed AR increased from 8.39% between 2012 and 2015 to 19.87% between 2016 and 2022 [2]. This upward trend underscores the need for effective

management strategies to mitigate the disease's burden on children and adolescents.

Current management of AR primarily involves pharmacotherapy with antihistamines and intranasal corticosteroids, which are considered the mainstay treatments. Immunotherapy is also recommended for cases where conventional treatments are insufficient, as it can prevent further allergic sensitizations and the development of asthma [3]. Despite these treatments, the objective assessment of treatment efficacy remains challenging. Traditionally, the success of AR treatment is measured through symptom relief and quality of life improvements, which are subjective and can vary widely among patients.

Quantitative nasal eosinophilia, the measurement of eosinophils in nasal secretions, offers an objective biomarker for evaluating the efficacy of AR treatments. Eosinophils are white blood cells involved in allergic inflammation, and their presence in nasal secretions correlates with the severity of allergic reactions. Recent studies suggest that monitoring nasal eosinophilia could provide a reliable means to optimize treatment regimens, particularly for intranasal corticosteroids, which are widely used in pediatric AR management [4].

This study aims to assess the role of quantitative nasal eosinophilia in optimizing intranasal topical steroid spray for the management of perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective cohort study design.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, over a period from December 2021 to September 2023.

Participants: A total of 50 pediatric patients diagnosed with perennial allergic rhinitis were enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pediatric patients aged 6-18 years.
- Diagnosed with perennial allergic rhinitis based on clinical history and diagnostic tests.
- Consent provided by guardians or parents for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with concurrent respiratory infections or chronic illnesses.
- Patients currently on systemic corticosteroids or other immunosuppressive treatments.

- Patients with nasal structural abnormalities that could interfere with the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the patient population meeting the inclusion criteria. Observer bias was mitigated by blinding the data analysts to the group assignments.

Data Collection: Data were collected at baseline and follow-up visits. Nasal eosinophil counts were measured quantitatively using nasal swabs analyzed under a microscope. Additional data included patient demographics, clinical history, and symptom severity scores.

Procedure: Patients were instructed to use the prescribed intranasal topical steroid spray as per the standard dosage guidelines. Follow-up visits were scheduled at regular intervals to monitor compliance and efficacy. Nasal swabs were collected during these visits for eosinophil count analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics and baseline characteristics. Paired t-tests were conducted to compare nasal eosinophil counts before and after treatment. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Multivariate analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders and assess the independent effect of the intranasal steroid spray on nasal eosinophilia.

Result

The study enrolled 50 pediatric patients, consisting of 28 males (56%) and 22 females (44%), with an age range of 6 to 18 years (mean age = 12.3 years, SD = 3.1).

The baseline characteristics of the study population are presented in Table 1. All participants had a confirmed diagnosis of perennial allergic rhinitis and none had significant comorbid conditions that could influence the study outcomes.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Variable	Value
Total Participants	50
Age (mean ± SD)	12.3 ± 3.1 years
Gender (Male/Female)	28/22
Duration of Allergic Rhinitis	3.5 ± 2.1 years

The primary outcome measured was the nasal eosinophil count, which was assessed at baseline and after the treatment period. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Nasal Eosinophil Counts Before and After Treatment

Time Point	Mean Eosinophil Count (cells/HPF)	SD	p-value
Baseline	15.2	4.3	
Post-Treatment	5.8	2.7	<0.001

The mean nasal eosinophil count at baseline was 15.2 cells/HPF (SD = 4.3). Following treatment with the intranasal topical steroid spray, the mean count significantly decreased to 5.8 cells/HPF (SD = 2.7), with a p-value of <0.001, indicating a statistically significant reduction.

In addition to eosinophil counts, symptom severity scores were recorded using a standardized questionnaire. The scores ranged from 0 (no symptoms) to 10 (severe symptoms). The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Symptom Severity Scores Before and After Treatment

Time Point	Mean Symptom Score	SD	p-value
Baseline	7.4	1.8	
Post-Treatment	3.1	1.6	<0.001

The mean symptom severity score decreased from 7.4 (SD = 1.8) at baseline to 3.1 (SD = 1.6) post-treatment. This reduction was also statistically significant, with a p-value of <0.001.

A multivariate regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders such as age, gender, and duration of allergic rhinitis. The analysis confirmed that the use of intranasal topical steroid spray was independently associated with a significant reduction in nasal eosinophil counts (p < 0.01).

No significant adverse effects were reported during the study period, indicating that the intranasal topical steroid spray was well-tolerated by the pediatric patients.

Discussion

The study investigated the efficacy of intranasal topical steroid spray in managing perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis by utilizing quantitative nasal eosinophilia as an objective measure. A total of 50 pediatric patients, with an almost equal gender distribution and a mean age of 12.3 years, participated in the study.

The results revealed a significant reduction in nasal eosinophil counts following treatment. At baseline, the mean eosinophil count was 15.2 cells/HPF, which decreased to 5.8 cells/HPF after the treatment period. This marked reduction, evidenced by a p-value of <0.001, indicates the effectiveness of the intranasal steroid spray in reducing nasal inflammation associated with allergic rhinitis. The significant drop in eosinophil counts underscores the potential of this treatment to mitigate the underlying inflammatory processes driving the symptoms of allergic rhinitis in pediatric patients.

Parallel to the reduction in eosinophil counts, there was a substantial improvement in symptom severity scores. The mean symptom score decreased from 7.4 at baseline to 3.1 post-treatment, with a statistically significant p-value of <0.001. This improvement highlights the clinical benefits of the treatment, translating the objective reduction in inflammation into perceptible relief for the patients. The notable decrease in symptom scores suggests that the intranasal steroid spray not only addresses

the biological markers of allergic rhinitis but also significantly enhances the quality of life for the pediatric patients.

Throughout the study, no significant adverse effects were reported, indicating that the intranasal topical steroid spray was well-tolerated among the participants. This is a crucial aspect, especially in pediatric populations, where the safety profile of treatments is paramount. The absence of adverse effects reinforces the suitability of intranasal steroid sprays as a safe option for long-term management of allergic rhinitis in children.

The findings from this study provide robust evidence that quantitative nasal eosinophilia can serve as an effective tool for optimizing the use of intranasal topical steroid sprays in pediatric allergic rhinitis. The significant reductions in both nasal eosinophil counts and symptom severity scores, coupled with the favorable safety profile, suggest that this treatment strategy can significantly improve clinical outcomes for children suffering from perennial allergic rhinitis. These results support the incorporation of quantitative nasal eosinophilia in clinical practice to tailor and enhance the management of allergic rhinitis in pediatric patients.

A study involving 300 children with perennial allergic rhinitis demonstrated that quantitative nasal eosinophilia (QNE) is an effective objective tool for optimizing intranasal steroid dosage. The study found significant improvements in both symptom scores and QNE scores after treatment with mometasone nasal spray [5].

Another study compared the symptomatic improvement and changes in nasal eosinophilia before and after short-term treatment with fluticasone furoate. Significant reductions in nasal eosinophilia and improvement in nasal and ocular symptoms were observed after one month of treatment [6].

Experimental evidence suggests that chronic intranasal corticosteroid use may cause degeneration of olfactory sensory neurons, raising concerns about long-term use for treating olfactory loss related to allergic rhinitis [7].

Mometasone furoate nasal spray has been shown to significantly reduce eosinophil and mast cell counts and improve quality of life in children with seasonal allergic rhinitis, with effects persisting even after discontinuation [8].

Comparing as-needed versus regular use of fluticasone furoate nasal spray, a study found that both methods resulted in similar improvements in symptom scores and quality of life, although regular use had a slight edge in nasal peak inspiratory flow improvements [9].

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that quantitative nasal eosinophilia is an effective objective tool for optimizing the use of intranasal steroid sprays in managing perennial pediatric allergic rhinitis. The significant reduction in nasal eosinophil counts and improvement in symptom severity scores highlight the potential of this approach to enhance treatment outcomes. Additionally, the treatment was well-tolerated with no significant adverse effects reported. These findings support the integration of nasal eosinophilia measurements into routine clinical practice to improve the management of allergic rhinitis in children. Further research with larger sample sizes and multi-centre trials is recommended to validate these results and explore long-term benefits.

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